

ASSOCIATIONS OF DIET QUALITY AND SLEEP QUALITY AMONG
OVERWEIGHT HOSTELITESSania Saher¹, Aman Ullah Khan², Zoha Noor³, Safina Tariq⁴, Ali Usman^{*5}, Fatima Abid⁶¹Lecturer, School of Allied Health Sciences SAHS, CMH Lahore Medical College and IOD, Lahore, Pakistan²Khyber Medical University Peshawar, Pakistan³Senior Clinical Nutritionist/Dietitian, City Hospital Bahawalpur, Pakistan⁴University Institute of Public Health, Islamabad, Pakistan⁵Ripha College of Rehabilitation and Allied Health Sciences, Sahiwal, Pakistan⁶Assistant Professor, UIDNS, The University of Lahore

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Ali Usman**Abstract**

Background: A diet having an optimal amount of macro and micro nutrients has a great impact on overall well being health and life quality. There is a strong and positive relationship between diet quality and sleep quality. This is a two way relationship in which each effect other in a complicated manner. **Objective:** The objective of this study is to assess the associations between diet and sleep quality among overweight hostelites.

Methods: A cross-sectional was conducted for period of 4months among 100 hostelite students of University of Lahore, Lahore, Pakistan. Data was collected using non-probability sampling technique. Healthy students of aged 18-30 years were recruited in study. Self-administered questionnaires were used to collect information on demographic characteristics, lifestyle factors (smoking status, alcohol drinking status, physical activity), sleep duration, sleep quality, and dietary habits. SPSS version 25.0 was used to tabulate and analyze data.

Results: The mean age of participants was 24.4851 ± 3.66773 whereas the mean age was 5.3645 ± 0.28331 . The weight readings ranged between 32kg to 103kg with mean of 63.3465 ± 12.35673 . Similarly the mean BMI was 23.9891 ± 5.03986 . Results showed a significant association between participants frequency of using electronic devices before sleep and their engagement in physical activity.

Conclusion: This findings of this study concluded that various factors affect dietary habits, sleep patterns, physical activity and stress management. Different strategies are required to promote healthy eating choices, improve sleep patterns and overall well being in targeted population. Future interventions should target modifiable factors identified in this study to support individuals in achieving healthier lifestyles and reducing the risk of obesity and related health issues.

INTRODUCTION

The occurrence of obesity is increasing worldwide in last few decades, presenting a remarkable challenge in field of public health. Most common age group affected by this surge is young adults because of their lifestyle and environmental factors (Luhar et al., 2020). Multiple factors contribute in prevalence of overweight and obesity among young adults but most common among them is commercialization of the food supply. This has led to the massive availability of cheap, highly processed foods high in calories, sugar, and unhealthy fats. This effortless access to fast food has greatly affect the food choices of young adults (Buoncristiano et al., 2021). Moreover, demanding lifestyles, limited interest in cooking peer pressure, limited physical activity, emotional eating, societal and cultural pressure are some other factors that lead to young adult's unhealthy food choices (Zubery et al., 2021), (Asif et al., 2020). The consequences of overweight and obesity among young adults are profound and far-reaching, encompassing both physical and psycho-social health outcomes. Obesity and overweight has severe and life long impact on life. Over deposition of fat in body that leads to obesity during young age can lead development of various diseases like type 2 diabetes, CVDs, different types of cancers and muscular disorders. (Quek et al., 2023). Diet quality and sleep quality are important part of human health and overall well being. Both factors work mutually to support optimal physical, psychological, mental well being, mood regulation and disease prevention (Wickham et al., 2020).

A diet having an optimal amount of macro and micro nutrients has a great impact on overall well being health and life quality (Martínez-de-Quel et al., 2021). Moreover, healthy dietary choices can lead to prevention of top five non communicable diseases (Clement-Carbonell et al., 2021). In addition to balanced diet, adequate and restful sleep also plays a crucial role in human health. A good sleep is important for restorative rest, cognitive functioning, and emotional regulation. While sleeping, body undergoes essential restorative and regenerative activities like tissue development, muscle recovery and learning process (Gothe et al., 2020).

Recent researches have showed a strong and positive relationship between diet quality and sleep quality. This is a two way relationship in which each effect

other in a complicated manner. Excessive intake of caffeine, alcohol, and fast food, emotional eating, disrupted eating habits and behavior can lead to inadequate and restless sleep (Zhao et al., 2020). Similarly disturbed sleep can alter appetite that in turn can lead to unnecessary food cravings, intake of high calories and reduced physical activity. All these factors can lead to metabolic disturbances and weight gain. Furthermore, ongoing sleep disruptions are associated with shifts in food choices, higher intake of calorie-rich foods, and a greater propensity for emotional eating triggered by stress or tiredness. Therefore, optimizing sleep and diet quality is important to maintain a healthy body-weight and prevention of non communicable diseases (Sanlier & Sabuncular, 2020).

The relationship between diet and sleep quality in overweight hostel residents is poorly understood, highlighting a major research gap among this age group. This research seeks to explore how these two factors are correlated and their effect on overall well being of overweight hostelites.

Methodology

A cross-sectional was conducted for period of 4months among 100 hostelite students of University of Lahore, Lahore, Pakistan. Data was collected using non-probability sampling technique. Healthy students of aged 18-30 years were recruited in study. Those students who were diagnosed with any pre-existing sleep disorders or conditions affecting sleep quality, such as sleep apnea, depression, anxiety or those on some sort of medications known to significantly impact sleep patterns or dietary habits, such as certain antidepressants or appetite suppressants were excluded from study. Self-administered questionnaires were used to collect information on demographic characteristics, lifestyle factors (smoking status, alcohol drinking status, physical activity), sleep duration, sleep quality, and dietary habits. SPSS version 25.0 was used to tabulate and analyze data. Required tables were produced by development of detailed syntaxes. Data analysis was done by following statistical methods:

- Descriptive analysis
- Chi-square test
- Graphical Presentation; Bar Figures

The rules and regulations set by the ethical committee of University of Lahore had been followed while conducting the research and the right of the research participants will be respected. Written informed consent had been taken from all the participants.

Table 1 shows the descriptive data for age, weight, height and body mass index (BMI) of participants. The mean age of participants was 24.4851 ± 3.66773 whereas the mean age was 5.3645 ± 0.28331 . The weight readings ranged between 32kg to 103kg with mean of 63.3465 ± 12.35673 . Similarly the mean BMI was 23.9891 ± 5.03986 .

Results

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for Age, Height, Weight and BMI:

Variables	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	100	18.00	37.00	24.4851	3.66773
Height	100	4.11	6.00	5.3645	.28331
Weight	100	32.00	103.00	63.3465	12.35673
BMI	100	13.80	49.00	23.9891	5.03986

Table 2 shows an association between participants frequency of using electronic devices before sleep and their engagement in physical activity. Physical activity was categorized into different types and participants

were asked to select one. There is a strong association between these two factors as $P < 0.05$ as shown in table below.

Table 2: Association between Use of Electronic Devices Before Sleep and Engagement in Physical Activity

Use electronic devices before going to sleep	Engage in physical activity					Total	P-value
	Running/Jogging, Walking	Cycling	Walking, Yoga/Pilates	Swimming, Cycling, Yoga/Pilates, Weightlifting	Other		
Never	1	0	3	0	2	6	0.028
Rarely	5	4	22	0	3	34	
Every day	4	2	9	1	2	18	

2-3 times a week	5	2	14	5	2	28
4-6 times a week	5	0	3	5	0	13
Total	20	8	51	11	9	99

Table 3: Association between Quality of Sleep and Trouble Falling Asleep or Staying Asleep

The data were analyzed to find another association between factors i.e association between sleep quality and trouble falling a sleep or staying asleep. A strong association was interpreted as $P < 0.034$ as show Table 3.

Quality of your sleep	Trouble falling asleep or staying asleep			Total	P-value
	No, never	Yes, occasionally	Rarely		
7-8 (good)	32	16	14	62	0.034
4-6 (fair)	11	19	8	38	
Total	43	35	22	100	

Table 4 shows association between participants sleep quality and their possible effect on daily life i.e tiredness during day time. There is no statistical significance between two factors as $P > 0.05$ as shown in table.

Table 4: Association between Feeling Well-Rested Upon Waking and Daytime Sleepiness or Fatigue

Feel well-rested when wake up	Feel sleepy or tired during the day			Total	P-value
	No, never	Yes, occasionally	Rarely		
Sometimes	8	13	5	26	0.104
Rarely	11	13	4	28	
Always	9	4	5	18	
Never	4	14	10	28	
Total	32	44	24	100	

Table 5 shows relationship between participant’s attempts to weight loss and the methods used for weight loss purpose. The table shows a significant statistical significance as $P < 0.05$.

Table 5: Association between Trying to Lose Weight and Rapid Weight Changes

Tried losing weight	Rapid weight changes		Total	P-value
	Yes	No		
Yes	18	17	35	0.035
No	20	45	65	
Total	38	62	100	

Table 6 shows relationship between frequency of weighing and eating meals outside. The statistical analysis of participant's response showed a non-significant relationship between both factors as $P > 0.05$.

Table 6: Association between Frequency of Weighing and Eating Meals Outside of Home

How often you weighed yourself	Meals outside of your home					Total	P-value
	1-2/month	2-3/month	3-4/month	4-5/month	more than five a month		
Yes	8	3	7	8	12	38	0.413
No	20	2	9	18	13	62	
Total	28	5	16	26	25	100	

Table 7 represents the relationship between the responses of participants preferred timings and their knowledge about caloric content of foods. Both of these factors were statistically non-significant as P -value > 0.05 .

Table 7: Association between Preferred Eating Schedule and Awareness of Caloric Content

Preferred eating schedule (e.g., intermittent fasting, small frequent meals)	Awareness about the caloric content of the foods			Total	P-value
	Rarely	Occasionally	Never		
Often	11	9	9	29	0.583
Sometimes	4	4	5	13	
All the time	11	8	3	22	
Rarely	13	9	14	36	
Total	39	30	31	100	

Data was statistically analyzed to find association between preferred eating schedule and awareness about sleeping hours. The statistical analysis showed non significant results as P -value > 0.05 .

Table 8: Association between Preferred Eating Schedule and Awareness about Sleeping Hours

Preferred eating schedule (e.g., intermittent fasting, small frequent meals)	Awareness about Sleeping hours			Total	P-value
	Not very aware	Yes, very aware	Moderately aware		
Often	6	14	9	29	0.50

Sometimes	4	6	3	13
All the time	12	8	2	22
Rarely	18	7	11	36
Total	40	35	25	100

Discussion

The demographic data of current study revealed that the mean age of participants was 24.49±3.67 years. This shows that young population mostly resides in hostels. Another study done in past also showed same results (Klein et al., 2004). Similarly the data of physical characteristics of participants revealed that mean height was 5.26ft and mean weight was 63.35kg. A similar study conducted by Hargens et al. (2013).

The data of current study revealed that they found it difficult to avoid like fast food, restaurant meant and salty and spicy snacks. Most of the participants used food just to overcome their stress and boredom. Previous research also showed similar results i.e the availability of food influences dietary behavior and choices of participants. Various psychological factors like stress and mood swings were linked to eating overeating and emotional eating (Konttinen et al., 2019).

Current study revealed that scheduled eating along with food portion was followed by 61% of participants. A past research showed that scheduled eating and portion control promote satiety and and regulate metabolism in body.(Ekmekcioglu & Touitou, 2011). This study showed that 45% participants were using electronic devices before sleeping. This habit can significantly effect the quality of sleep. A past study revealed that using electronic devices before sleeping can lead to over consumption of caffeine and calorie dense foods(Bradbury et al., 2019).

The current study revealed that 60% of participants were engaged in physical activity for three times per week whereas 40% were not physically active mostly. A previous study revealed that regular physical activity can promote healthy eating and can overall sleep quality (Whitaker et al., 2014).

Conclusion

This findings of this study concluded that various factors affect dietary habits, sleep patterns, physical activity and stress management. Different strategies are required to promote healthy eating choices,

improve sleep patterns and overall well being in targeted population. The assessment of relationship between diet and sleep quality and their effect on physical activity and stress management can provide a valuable in-sight in current literature on life style and overall well being among young adults residing in hostels.

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